

Synthesis of Biflavans from 6-Hydroxyflavanones

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SEVERAL workers¹⁻⁵ believed that the coloured substances formed during the reduction of flavanoid compounds are flavylum salts. This view is based, partly, upon the superficial visual similarity of colours between the substances produced and the flavylum salts. Bisflavenylidenes⁶, flav-3-enes⁷⁻⁸ and flav-2-enes⁹ have been identified among the zinc reductive acetylation products of flavones and flavonols. Russel and Clark⁹ showed that the reduction of chalcones produced compounds which are qualitatively indistinguishable from the natural phlobatannins.

Experimental

During the present work 6, 2'- and 6, 3'-dihydroxyflavanones¹⁰ were treated with zinc in acidic media when these underwent bimolecular reduction yielding the corresponding biflavans I a & b (m. p. s 138° (d.) and 130° (d.) respectively), along with some resinous products. These biflavans turn black on exposure to air and moisture. The structures of the resinous products have not been established and these are probably the self condensed products of the flavan-4-ols which are also formed during the reduction of flavanones.

The elemental analysis and the molecular weight determination of the biflavans I(a & b) were in

agreement with the molecular formula, C₃₀H₂₆O₈. The biflavans were separated from the mixtures by column chromatography using silica gel. The purity of I(a & b) and their methyl ethers was tested by TLC on silica gel in toluene-formic acid (1 : 3) as irrigating solvent.

The absence of ketonic absorption in the IR spectra showed that the 6, 2'- and 6, 3'-dihydroxyflavanones were reduced. The reduced products were methylated with diazomethane. Zeisel estimation indicated the presence of four methoxyl groups in each of the methylated product. The methyl ethers of I(a & b), m. p. s 126° (d) and 123° (d.) respectively, showed absorption bands for the hydroxyl groups (3350 - 3450cm⁻¹) in the IR spectra and also underwent acetylation to yield a diacetate (ν_{max} KBr 1740 cm⁻¹) showing the presence of two alcoholic hydroxyl groups. Thus it was shown that the reduced products contain two alcoholic hydroxyls and four phenolic hydroxyl groups. The phenolic methyl ethers of I(a & b) when treated with sodium metaperiodate, consumed one mole of the periodate per mole of the compound, showing, thereby the presence of I-4, II-4-diol grouping (1, 2-glycolic system) in (I a & b).

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(I)

a :	R	R ₁
b :	OH	H
	H	OH

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